

Why is investing in human capital in rural areas important in less-developed countries? One argues that building schools in rural areas reduces income inequality between rural and urban areas. Do you agree? Why do you agree or disagree?

(ES30035: Coursework)

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Section A

Q3. Why is investing in human capital in rural areas important in less-developed countries?

One argues that building schools in rural areas reduces income inequality between rural and urban areas. Do you agree? Why do you agree or disagree?

Human capital is 'the stock of knowledge, skills and other personal characteristics embodied in people that helps them to be productive' (OECD, n.d.). Investing in these assets, primarily health and education, constitutes direct investment in people and is fundamental to economic development, especially in less-developed countries (LDCs). Throughout this essay, we examine how rural human capital investment affects rural-urban inequality, assuming that individuals in rural areas are largely unskilled agricultural workers in a labour-intensive, low-productivity sector (Christiaensen and Maertens, 2022).

Rural-urban inequality accounts for 40% of mean country inequality, and an even larger proportion in more unequal countries (Young, 2013). This disparity stems largely from rural-urban human capital differences; agricultural workers have around half the schooling of other workers, with limited access to quality education and healthcare (Gollin et al., 2014). The stark productivity differences between urban and rural areas in LDCs will likely persist without adequate human capital development in rural areas.

A key strength of human capital investment is the complementarities between its components, particularly health and education. Better healthcare enhances returns to educational investment through improved school attendance and quality of learning, while a higher life expectancy increases lifetime returns to education. Simultaneously, superior education improves health outcomes through a better understanding of hygiene and disease. It will also produce more doctors and teachers in future periods, which is crucial given the lack of educated, willing teachers in rural areas who can deliver quality education (Yusuph, 2013). This creates a self-reinforcing virtuous cycle, which is essential for breaking intergenerational poverty cycles in rural areas with poor infrastructure.

Early childhood investment in human capital is crucial, as Heckman (2008) notes; 'the longer society waits to intervene in the life cycle of a disadvantaged child, the more costly it is to remediate disadvantage'. This is especially relevant to rural areas in LDCs, where children are often born into poverty, facing poor nutrition and healthcare, with limited development opportunities.

Building on this, early-stage investments must be compounded with additional investments as childhood development progresses to maximise their returns. This occurs through two channels, as

identified by Cunha and Heckman (2007). The first is self-productivity, where skills developed early persist in future periods. The second is dynamic complementarity, in which skills learnt at early stages of development boost the productivity of future investments. Together, these can produce multiplier effects, through which ‘skills beget skills and abilities beget abilities’, as succinctly put by Cunha and Heckman. For example, learning to read at an early age sets a good foundation and increases the returns of later education.

These mechanisms highlight the importance of sustained investment in rural human capital to reduce inequality. The lack of early childhood investment in rural areas, where children face limited access to quality education, health issues and inadequate nutrition, can cause early disadvantages to build up rapidly. A World Bank study in Indonesia found that Early Childhood Education and Development (ECED) investments improve children’s readiness for future learning and boost returns to education (Hyson et al., 2013). This suggests that simply building schools in rural areas without addressing early development issues limit the policy’s potential to boost rural human capital and reduce rural-urban inequality.

The policy does not specify which type of schools are to be built, but evidence from Ethiopia suggests that while primary school enrolment rates are similar in rural and urban areas, there is a stark difference in secondary school attendance, which correlates with rural students facing higher average distances to schools and longer travel times (Cuesta, 2018). This suggests that policy should address the lack of available secondary schools, which prevents students from building on their primary education to maximise returns on their initial investment.

However, an issue with this supply-side policy is that it assumes that access to education is the primary constraint, but we must also examine the demand-side factors to fully understand why enrolment rates are low in rural areas of LDCs.

In LDCs, education is generally viewed as an investment, as households with a tight budget cannot afford education without a perceived return. Furthermore, parents often make this schooling decision on their children’s behalf despite potentially not profiting from the returns.

As with any investment decision, parents consider the costs of education, including the direct costs, such as fees and equipment, but also the often higher indirect costs of schooling, primarily foregone income from child labour. This opportunity cost is particularly significant in the labour-intensive agricultural sector, as children are often required to work. This is again compounded by poor infrastructure, such as healthcare, where shorter life expectancies and widespread disease increase the value of child labour.

The decision to use child labour can be understood through two key principles developed by Basu and Van (1998). The 'luxury axiom' outlines a situation where parents only utilise child labour when household income falls below subsistence levels and child labour is necessary for household survival. On the other hand, the 'substitution axiom' describes a situation in which households with income above the subsistence level choose child labour over education to boost immediate household income, viewing adult and child labour as imperfect substitutes in production.

With low perceived returns to education, parents may choose child labour over schooling in the substitution axiom. Jensen (2010) asked eighth-grade male students from the Dominican Republic what they expect to earn in the future, aged 30-40, under different education scenarios. He found that while actual returns to secondary education show a 41% increase in earnings, students perceived only an 8% return. This perception gap is even wider for tertiary education. He finds this difference starker in rural areas, where few adults are well-educated and have little basis to infer potential returns, a sentiment they will likely pass on to their children. Interestingly, he found primary education to be the exception, with returns perceived to be marginally higher than they are.

Therefore, children of secondary school age and above may face particularly low education participation rates, even when schooling is available. On top of facing low perceived returns to education, they are more productive than younger children, so their labour is more valuable. Therefore, building schools alone may be insufficient, and policy must align perceived and real returns to education and relieve economic constraints that drive families to prioritise child labour.

Furthermore, even if the policy succeeds in increasing rural education, we need to analyse the more fundamental challenge of whether it will reduce rural-urban income inequality. The returns to education among agricultural workers are lower than in other sectors, as there is less use for education in the industry (Herrendorf and Schoellman, 2018). Therefore, educated rural citizens often migrate to urban areas to achieve a higher wage and maximise their returns to schooling, a phenomenon known as 'human capital flight' or the 'brain drain'.

Young (2013) provides important insights into the dynamics of rural-urban migration, finding that the average rural-urban migrant is more educated than the average rural resident, while the average urban-rural migrant is less educated than the average urban resident.

He proposes that workers 'sort' themselves between rural and urban areas based on skills and education. This occurs as urban areas have a higher relative demand for skilled labour, while rural areas have a higher relative demand for unskilled labour. He finds that when there is very little difference in the skill intensity of production in urban and rural areas, the urban-rural gap in living

standards completely disappears. This indicates that rural-urban inequality is driven largely by structural economic differences. By this metric, an increase in rural education without addressing these structural differences would simply increase the rural-urban migration of educated workers.

Harris and Todaro (1970) propose a dual-economy model to capture migration from rural to urban areas and derive rural wages. They consider an economy with a rural sector paying wage w_R , an urban formal sector with wage w_F and an urban informal sector with wage w_I , where $w_F > w_R > w_I$. We assume for simplicity that rural workers can migrate to urban areas with no cost, and must live where they work, and w_F and w_I are exogenous and fixed.

Migrating workers secure formal sector jobs with probability P_F and informal sector jobs with probability P_I , based on the proportion of jobs in each sector;

$$P_F = \left(\frac{L_F}{L_F + L_I} \right)$$

$$P_I = 1 - P_F = \left(\frac{L_I}{L_F + L_I} \right)$$

The expected wage from migrating is;

$$\left(\frac{L_F}{L_F + L_I} \right) w_F + \left(\frac{L_I}{L_F + L_I} \right) w_I$$

In equilibrium, workers are indifferent between migrating and not migrating;

$$\left(\frac{L_F}{L_F + L_I} \right) w_F + \left(\frac{L_I}{L_F + L_I} \right) w_I = w_R$$

This framework demonstrates how individuals make rational migration decisions by comparing expected urban wages to rural wages, based on the probability of securing a formal sector job and wage differentials. However, by treating rural workers as homogeneous, the model fails to capture how education levels affect a migrant's probability of securing a high-paid job. By extending it to incorporate education, we can analyse how investment in schooling in rural areas affects the migration decision and consequently rural-urban inequality.

We therefore make some simple adjustments to incorporate education into the model. We assume that the formal urban sector is skilled, so requires some baseline level of education (an observable proxy for skill). We implement a variable $0 \leq E \leq 1$, representing an individual's education level, and a variable $0 < \bar{E} < 1$ representing the minimum education required for a formal sector job, which is exogenous and varies depending on the structure of an economy.

We also introduce a variable $0 < \theta < \frac{L_F + L_I}{(1 - \bar{E})L_F}^1$, which represents the extent to which education improves P_F . The parameter $\frac{L_F + L_I}{(1 - \bar{E})L_F}$ ensures $P_F < 1$ and has some economic sense; the upper bound on θ is highest when formal jobs are scarce relative to informal jobs, and a high baseline education requirement requires very high levels of education.

A migrating worker with $E < \bar{E}$ cannot find a formal sector job, so $P_F = 0, P_I = 1$. As $w_R > w_I$, this individual will not migrate.

A worker with $E \geq \bar{E}$ faces the following probabilities of joining the formal (skilled) or informal (unskilled) sectors;

$$P_F = \theta(E - \bar{E}) \left(\frac{L_F}{L_F + L_I} \right)$$

$$P_I = 1 - P_F$$

We include a linear relationship between P_F and E for simplicity, but a concave relationship may be more realistic in displaying diminishing marginal returns to education in obtaining a formal sector job.

As previously stated, in LDCs, a parent may only invest in education if they expect to see a return; so their child's expected lifetime earnings with education – cost of education $>$ lifetime earnings without education; for any $E \geq \bar{E}$;

$$n \left[\theta(E - \bar{E}) \left(\frac{L_F}{L_F + L_I} \right) \right] w_F + n \left[1 - \left[\theta(E - \bar{E}) \left(\frac{L_F}{L_F + L_I} \right) \right] \right] w_I - C(E) > n w_R$$

$C(E)$ represents the direct and indirect costs of achieving E , with $C'(E) > 0$ and $C''(E) > 0$ reflecting that direct schooling costs and foregone earnings increase at accelerating rates for higher education levels. n represents expected years worked, and is used to calculate expected lifetime earnings from each sector.

As any individual with $E < \bar{E}$ does not migrate, this holds in equilibrium.

An individual with access to schooling optimises their level of education;

¹ We find the upper bound on θ by setting $P_F = 1, E = 1$ in $P_F = \theta(E - \bar{E}) \left(\frac{L_F}{L_F + L_I} \right)$

$$\max_E \left[n \left[\theta(E - \bar{E}) \left(\frac{L_F}{L_F + L_I} \right) \right] w_F + n \left[1 - \left[\theta(E - \bar{E}) \left(\frac{L_F}{L_F + L_I} \right) \right] \right] w_I - C(E) \right]$$

$$s. t. 0 \leq E \leq 1$$

The individual will choose the (non-zero) level of education for which perceived marginal benefits equal marginal cost, as shown in *Figure 1*. Individuals then compare their expected returns from migration against w_R to decide whether to undertake education and migrate.

Figure 1

We can use this analysis and some intuition to measure the impact of increased education on rural-urban inequality.

Building schools gives rural workers with above-average natural ability and productivity increased access to education, allowing them to develop their skills and signal their capabilities to employers. The expected urban wage grows with higher education, and rural-urban migration increases as more workers obtain education above the threshold level.

This creates two competing effects on the rural economy. The 'brain drain' effect from the most educated (and therefore productive) workers migrating means that rural productivity will likely decrease. This is compounded by a reduction in knowledge spillovers and the weakening of institutions in rural areas such as hospitals and schools, which could create a downward spiral. However, a smaller rural labour force may push up average rural wages due to diminishing marginal returns to labour in the agricultural sector in LDCs (Johnson, 1993). Therefore, the impact on rural-urban inequality is ambiguous.

This model implies that education alone has a weak impact on rural-urban income inequality. Any reduction in inequality is simply caused by an increase in rural-urban migration improving per-capita wages, rather than productivity gain from improved education.

For rural education to effectively reduce income inequality, steps need to be taken to address these problems. *Figure 2* illustrates a situation in which an individual's initial marginal benefit (MB_1) and marginal cost (MC_1) curves do not intersect for any value $E \geq \bar{E}$, so despite the availability of schooling, optimal education is zero. Policies which cut the information gap on returns to education increase the perceived marginal benefits from MB_1 to MB_2 , while alleviating household poverty reduces the marginal costs from MC_1 to MC_2 , creating a positive equilibrium $E^* \geq \bar{E}$.

Figure 2

Therefore, while building schools is an important component of reducing rural-urban income inequality, it is insufficient in isolation, and complementary policies are essential. Firstly, the perceived information gap about returns to education must be addressed, and household poverty constraints limiting educational participation must be alleviated. Secondly, rural infrastructure investments must address structural differences and prevent the 'brain drain'. The development of rural credit markets in particular allows educated agricultural workers to borrow and invest in capital to boost productivity. Finally, any policy must create direct incentives for educated workers to work in rural areas.

China's 'Special Post Teachers Program' demonstrates the challenges of policy implementation. The program recruits recent university graduates to teach in rural schools, offering competitive salaries and other benefits such as career advancement opportunities. However, Wu and Song (2023) find struggles with long-term teacher retention, as broader quality-of-life urban-rural disparities such as

non-wage working and living conditions and access to services deter teachers. This demonstrates that even well-designed policy interventions may fail if the urban-rural structural differences are not addressed.

This analysis demonstrates that while building rural schools may marginally reduce income inequality, meaningful impact requires policy to simultaneously improve human capital and invest in rural areas to make them attractive places for educated workers to work and live. Once these barriers are lifted, investment in rural schools can create a sustained reduction in rural-urban inequality, and we can reach our desired equilibrium in which educated individuals are truly indifferent between working in rural and urban areas;

$$P_F w_F + P_I w_I = P_{SR} w_{SR} + P_{UR} w_{UR}$$

Where P_{SR} is a function of E and represents the probability of an educated worker finding a skilled rural job paying w_{SR} . P_{UR} is not a function of E , and represents the probability of an educated worker finding an unskilled rural job, with wage w_{UR} . $w_{SR} > w_{UR}$.

2420 words

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